

Recognition, incentives and research assessment

Interview with Elizabeth Gadd

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Sousa, Jose P 0:16

It would be interesting to start with a more general question so that we can compare the different answers that we have from different perspectives, so the first question will be: what do you think are the three main challenges we are facing to develop an Open Research culture in academia?

Elizabeth Gadd 1:05

Defining an Open Research culture is a start. With the fact that there's so much research culture work going on at the moment, I think Open Research is probably looking to find its place a little bit within the rest of the Open Research culture work that's going on.

There's been so much focus on Open Research and Open Access for so long, there have been dedicated teams, dedicated resource, and I think the lens is broadening now.

There's the whole range of other related issues around research assessment, around research culture, around recognition and reward, and around research integrity, that Open Research, I suppose, is trying to find its place within this broader umbrella of activity.

And it's so interrelated, particularly to things like research integrity and research culture and values that are very high level, and that's kind of one of its main challenges going forward.

There's been a lurch from "What are the main draws?" [to] "What are the main things that are holding people back from engaging with Open Research?" And people have automatically leapt on the incentives. We were assessing the wrong things.

We're valuing the wrong things, and if we only valued the right things, then people would naturally start to engage with them because they'll be motivated to engage with Open Research because they'll be being assessed on it.

'If we care, if we value Open Research, we should be assessing Open Research' is a bit of a narrative historically, and I think that's a false assumption. It's a problematic assumption because if you start doing that with all these new things that we care about, Open Research and research integrity and research culture and everything else, you're just going to end up with trying to assess so many things that everything gets lost.

And a lot of institutions are now starting to add Open Research to their promotion criteria, for example. But it's amongst so many other things, no actual weighting is placed on it. No real clear mechanism for assessing it is being developed, and so it's just kind of sitting there as a bit of a boasting point for institutions.

So, it's not actually making much difference in terms of institutional engagement with Open Research. I think there needs to be a kind of a shift towards more baseline expectations for Open Research.

And so something around Open Research finding its place within a broader research culture, a focus on how we assess or incentivise it.

If I was going to choose a third, it's just that some people are a bit jaded with it all and feel like it's done and dusted. "We've done Open Research, haven't we?"

And then I think there's another cohort, some parts of the community have just not been really exposed to any expectations around Open Research at all. And those of us who deal with it every day think everyone knows what they're doing, and they're making their work available, openly engaging with these sorts of things. But on the ground, when you speak to actual researchers, there's a lot of them [who] have absolutely no idea what the expectations [are] – this is certainly what we're experiencing locally, anyway.

So, that's another kind of big challenge. It's keeping it fresh. Both in the minds of those who are seeking to deliver it, the administrators and professional services seeking to support it, but also the researchers who we need to action and live out Open Research practices.

Khan, Hamid 7:01

One thing I wanted to draw out there was around this definition of Open Research. Is it that actually it's just not very well defined and Open Research can mean anything to anyone at the moment?

Elizabeth Gadd 7:17.

Yes, and I think Open Research, like research culture probably, does definitely mean different things to different institutions, to different organisations, to funders, to different disciplines. I think that's part of the problem.

At Loughborough, we focus on three main domains, which is open access to outputs, open data and open methods essentially, but that excludes quite a lot of other stuff. There's nothing around citizenship and open education and preregistration, and all sorts of other elements that you could put under the Open Research umbrella.

Different institutions care about different things. Different disciplines can engage with different things, and so I definitely think that's part of the challenge.

Khan, Hamid 8:30

Can you tell us a little bit about CoARA, and where it came from? What's it seeking to do? What's your role within it?

Elizabeth Gadd 8:41

CoARA is [the] Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment. Its constitutive assembly was in December 2022, so it's quite nascent. Its founding document is the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment, and anyone was invited to be a part of the conversation, which led to the development of that document.

It is essentially ten principles, ten commitments for delivering more responsible forms of research assessment. Given all the challenges in the sector around

assessment practices leading to poor behaviours and practices, including lack of engagement with Open Research, but not exclusively, Open Research was a big driver of CoARA, that's fair to say, but it's not the only driver.

[There are] four core commitments around avoiding poor use of publication indicators, around evaluating a broader diversity of things, around avoiding the use of rankings in our research assessments and moving more towards qualitative over quantitative forms of assessment. Those are the four core commitments and then there [are] six supporting commitments, which are essentially the means by which institutions might deliver on those four core commitments: committing resources, sharing best practice, developing new methods and building the evidence base around more responsible forms of research assessment.

The General Assembly consists of all the members who've both signed up and agreed to form part of the coalition. There's a steering board, which governs the day-to-day activities. It's got 13 different working groups working on different areas of assessment reform that we need to improve on. And there's now 16 national chapters. Countries can get together and agree that they want to work on those issues that might be unique to that particular region.

And obviously there's a lot of government policy and local practices that often need addressing within a particular region.

Elizabeth Gadd 11:31

In terms of how it builds on DORA [the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment], DORA was very much involved in the creation of CoARA. Two of the CoARA's core principles are taken directly from DORA, and that's around valuing a broader range of things and avoiding poor use of publication indicators. DORA are observers on the CoARA Steering Board, so they're very much our allies and friends, and we're working together towards a similar goal with this slightly different approach.

DORA is over ten years old now, so I think it's fair to say that CoARA's really learned a lot from the DORA experience. DORA is still doing amazing things globally; it's got really good global engagement. And CoARA is seeking to achieve the same things

through different mechanisms. CoARA builds on a lot of historical approaches to responsible research assessment [including the Leiden Manifesto].

Khan, Hamid 12:32

You mentioned the idea of valuing a broader diversity of things. It was interesting [that] you said shifting the culture of recognition is not necessarily going to embed Open Research practice. But would it be fair to say that it's a necessary step, even if not a sufficient one?

Elizabeth Gadd 12:54

It is. Reforming research assessment is critical to getting engagement with Open Research. It's just we shouldn't then automatically leap to assessing Open Research and Open Research alone and thinking that's going to fix things, because it won't. So, it is absolutely an important part of delivering on Open Research engagement.

Khan, Hamid 13:19

Our 'Beyond Open Research' project is looking at trying to embed a culture of quality and reliability within Imperial's research, which is not to say that there aren't already examples of good practice happening.

It's about taking that systemic and cultural approach based on what we've said here about broadening the diversity of things that matter. What do you think are those things that might matter? What are the contributions to research and the outputs of it that we should be recognising and incentivising in order to embed a culture of quality and reliability?

Elizabeth Gadd 14:01

We should be setting a threshold around our expectations for engagement with Open Research practices, just like we have with health and safety guidelines in our labs. You just have to do it because if you don't, then the research isn't going to be of quality [and] you're going to fall foul of regulations relating to health and safety.

There should be expectations set either at discipline or national or institutional level around engagement with practices that the institution believes are going to lead to higher quality research. And I think that's where the incentivisation should come from. The fact that at this institution you preregister your research, that's just how we

do research at Loughborough, Imperial... wherever it might be. We make our data open unless there's a good reason why not.

At Loughborough, we promote CRediT [the Contributor Role Taxonomy] when developing journal articles, there should be these kind of baseline expectations. If you really believe in the power of Open Research to deliver higher quality, more reliable research, then we need to just get serious about setting out the standards with our communities [and] supporting researchers to adhere to those standards. And the [trickiest] bit of discipline in research is when they don't adhere to those standards.

It should be a hygiene factor. That's how I always describe it. And just as we would expect folk to adhere to our EDI policies and all the other things that we really care about that are really important, we should be setting the standards for how researchers practice, and Open Research should be clearly a part of that.

That's not to say that we've got that yet, but if you're talking about incentivising, you've got to do that first. I think it doesn't need incentivising, it's just bad practice needs disincentivising. We shouldn't be giving people a pat on the back when they make their data available. We should expect everyone to make their data available and be dealing with individuals that don't achieve that, assuming that they've had all the support and the necessary guidance. But many institutions [aren't] there yet.

Khan, Hamid 17:54

That leads us to talk about the things that universities and institutions can do by themselves. Does it necessarily require action from higher up, from funders and publishers and governments, or can it be done institutionally?

Elizabeth Gadd 18:13

Increasingly, in my experience, and I've been developing publications strategy training for a decade, it's been interesting seeing over that decade how researchers' views have changed and attitudes have changed towards the institutions.

Ten years ago, folk would come in and it's almost irrelevant to them where they work. Their loyalty is to their discipline, and if there are norms and standards in their

discipline, they will adhere to those above all else. They [didn't] really care too much for what [their] institution [said]. Now I've seen it completely flipped. This training we deliver here is largely aimed at early career researchers and new lecturers, and they want to know what the rules are, but from the institution: how they are going to pass their probation, what they need to do. And if you tell them clearly what the rules are, they will stick to those rules. They care now about what the institution says.

I guess it's because that's where the money is. Particularly these folk on probation, they want to ensure that their income remains. So, anything where there's funding attached -- funders obviously have got huge amount of power, REF [the Research Excellence Framework] has a huge amount of power, UK research funders, Research Councils, have a huge amount of power for setting the standards around Open Research engagement.

We've seen that with Open Access. The UK, if you compare us to the rest of the world, we're significantly higher. We did have significantly higher engagement until it just became a matter of money, basically, and who's got enough money to pay for APCs [Article Processing Charges]. And then, of course, those who've got the money tend to do better, or parts of the world where they don't care about publishing in certain journals which require APCs, and they've always published Diamond Open Access; their rates for Open Access publishing are high too. But, we know that the bottom line is money. That's where huge incentives come from.

Khan, Hamid 21:07

It's interesting that you mentioned the Open Access case. I've always been fascinated by this as an exemplar, because we talk a lot about recognising and incentivising things, but the thing that really shifted the dial was the UKRI mandate, and universities having the infrastructure in terms of repositories to be able to handle that mandate. Is it just a case of providing infrastructure and then saying you have to do this?

Elizabeth Gadd 21:38

Yes, I think so. I think that those norms and standards come from somewhere and the Open Access norm in the UK came originally from UKRI, but ultimately REF,

because that then applied to everybody. There's obviously that Open Research culture change pyramid that Brian Nosek put together.

I would switch the last two around, policy and incentivisation, but you can't expect people to do things and not provide them with the means to do it. You've got to get the infrastructure right, which includes not only the physical ability to do something, but the know-how and the support. I think that's probably the challenge for a lot of institutions, particularly less well-funded ones. Ultimately, I think, it does boil down to that.

Khan, Hamid 23:01

Could you, then, give some examples, if you've got any, of things that are already being done at other institutions or in other countries that you're aware of from your CoARA experience in order to reform recognition and incentives and assessment in order to embed things like Open Research? What's already going on that's out there?

Elizabeth Gadd 23:31

Well, there are two big European projects. There's GraspOS¹ and Opus².

GraspOS is using the SCOPE framework³ to support the delivery of Open Research aware assessments, recognising that Open Research is not in itself enough to deliver better quality research, and nor is it the only thing that institutional assessment should focus on. It's got a whole range of stakeholders who are part of the consortium, and they're all looking to use this kind of SCOPE-based framework to implement different forms of Open Research based assessments in different settings.

The Opus project is focussing more on metrics and counts of things: at institutional level, how many data sets you have got and how many researchers preregister the research, etc., which I don't think is nuanced enough for this space, personally. They are looking at engaging with Open Infrastructure for Responsible Research Assessment, so OpenAIRE⁴ to see what data they should be asking of institutions to

¹ See [About - GraspOS](#) [accessed: 2-9-2024].

² See [OPUS Home - Open and Universal Science \(OPUS\) Project \(opusproject.eu\)](#) [accessed: 02-9-2024].

³ See [SCOPE Framework for Research Evaluation | INORMS](#) [accessed: 2-9-2024].

⁴ See [Open Infrastructure for Responsible Research Assessment \(openaire.eu\)](#) [accessed: 2-9-2024].

report on so that some kind of benchmarking can take place. It's been a while since I've seen what's going on, but that's my understanding of those two big projects.

There's a lot of institutions developing career assessment matrixes now based on the Open Science career assessment matrix (OS-CAM) and Norway's got NOR-CAM. There might be a FIN-CAM coming up, so different institutions in Finland are certainly developing these sorts of things, so it's a way of assessing researchers in a more rounded way so it includes Open Research aspects.

Obviously, a lot of institutions in the UK and beyond are looking at putting Open Research expectations in their recruitment criteria, promotion criteria and so on, but again, it's not always as effective as it could be, because of the way that it's been weighted or not weighted and not really made clear how it was going to be assessed.

Something we're piloting at Loughborough is called evidence-informed output narratives. For internal processes, we're looking for where outputs are part of those assessments, and we have developed an approach whereby researchers will be invited to supply a short narrative on up to three outputs, which is evidenced from a menu of existing indicators which have been weighted by the disciplines within each school.

So, then, when it comes to a likely non-expert assessor to compare a promotion application from somebody from the arts with somebody from the sciences, they will be able to compare those narratives, see the evidence, and they'll be able to compare the weight of that evidence and hopefully make a more fair and informed judgment on those outputs.

We are hoping to pilot that in the autumn here at Loughborough, to see how it works for both the assessors and the assessed.

Khan, Hamid 27:55

Just picking up on that last one there around what you're doing at Loughborough, the evidence-informed output narratives, what kind of outputs do you think people will be looking to evidence or what kind of outputs do you want them to talk about?

Elizabeth Gadd 28:01

Well, anything, essentially, they could submit. For example, in our arts and humanities we have a lot of practising artists at Loughborough. So it might be that they want to put forward a sculpture or poem or it could be a standard journal article.

One thing I didn't mention, the dimensions on which they will be asked to provide evidence is around their contribution, but [also] the quality and the visibility. The visibility is where we would see Open Research expectations being made manifest. And, obviously, an expectation that the output will be made openly available will be a requirement across the piece. Folk will need to provide evidence for that. That's the point, when you're comparing different types of output from different disciplines, you'll hopefully be able to make a fair assessment by using this mechanism. That's the plan.

Khan, Hamid 29:27

I'm intrigued to know how you would evaluate the quality of a piece of research that is submitted as a sculpture or a poem because it's a completely abstract way of thinking about quality, isn't it?

Elizabeth Gadd 29:48

Some of the indicators are around peer review comments and peer review scores because we have an annual output review process at Loughborough, which is partly developmental, partly with one eye on the REF, so that, when we come to 2028, we don't have to look down the back of the sofa for outputs and see which our strongest might be.

When it's a non-expert assessor assessing these outputs, which it often is for internal processes, having access to expert assessments, which might be a couple of lines from a peer reviewer report, it could be a peer review score, it could be the number of people who attended your exhibition. It could be anything like that [that] will hopefully give them a chance to make a better judgment.

As I say, we're still due to pilot it; it might not work, but it was co-designed with the community over a number of years, so it has been a long time in the making. I'm

hoping it will help provide fair assessments and an easier job for assessors when doing that important work.

Khan, Hamid 31:15

Are you concerned that, with this being a system that's very specific to Loughborough, it might disadvantage people that are applying externally for jobs at other institutions?

Elizabeth Gadd 31:29

No, because, increasingly, universities, certainly in the UK, are all going down a similar road – they're looking for narratives. We're all recognising that, certainly narrative CVs, they're everywhere now. And getting into the mode of creating narrative about our work, a key element of which will be the output from that work, is a really good skill to develop and something that could be repurposed in different forms of assessment.

There's a recognition that narratives alone can quickly become a fiction. If I'm telling you that my output is marvellous and has had a massive impact, you're going to say "Prove it", right? And that's when you need to start getting into: "Here's the evidence for my statement". So, we can't just have narratives without any evidence whatsoever, and that's what we're trying to build on there, how do you build a narrative that's evidence based? And I think that's the future.

We're helping our researchers to get into a mindset by which they describe, in an evidenced way, their contributions.

Khan, Hamid 32:52

And it goes back to what you were saying about focussing more on the qualitative side of assessment, rather than quantitative. The elephant in the room is really around metrics, isn't it? There's this tendency to try to measure everything. How do you see the role of metrics going forward? Is there a role for metrics, or will we always just end up creating perverse incentives and gamification?

Elizabeth Gadd 33:30

When you say metrics, I'm assuming you mean publication metrics, is that right?

Khan, Hamid 33:36

I mean if we found a way of quantifying people's engagement with Open Research practices, for example, and we slapped a number on it and said, "You did this much Open Research", to be very crude, that's the kind of thing I'm talking about.

Elizabeth Gadd 33:56

It depends on what level of granularity we're talking. Indicators can be really helpful. Data can be really helpful. We need it. Look at gender pay gap data. It's been transformative across the sector. We need numbers. Are numbers at the level of the individual meaningful? No. They're just very rarely meaningful. We'll use them in certain contexts.

When I'm asked this question "What do you think about metrics?", we have to first think about the context. Because if we're talking about using numbers to decide whether you get the job or I get the job, then that's likely to be highly problematic.

If we're talking about numbers to compare whether Loughborough or Imperial produced more research last year, they can be very helpful because we can count those things. At the level of a university, we can do quite a lot with the data because they're big numbers. Well, perhaps Imperial and Loughborough are not very good examples, because Imperial has no arts and humanities, really.

When you're comparing like with like, a large scale like that, of course the numbers can be very helpful to us. Depending on the size of the entity you're talking about, depending on the purpose for which you're doing the assessment, and depending on the discipline in which those entities operate, you can use metrics at some larger-scale forms of assessment.

For lower levels of granularity, it becomes more problematic. Whether you're counting Open Access publications or citations, or how much grant income you've got, or how many PhD students you have, you're just going to need a lot of context.

The nub of responsible research assessment is, to what extent do we balance out the qualitative and the quantitative forms of assessment? Because we will need both in every single setting, even if I'm looking at Imperial production levels relative to Loughborough, as you need to know how many more students, how many more staff there are at Imperial relative to Loughborough in order to understand that data and make some sense of it. You'll need context, which may be numbers, but it's largely likely to be some form of qualitative narrative.

But we always end up gaming. In terms of gamification and perverse incentives, I always say: where there's a prize, there's a game. Because we associate prizes with games, don't we? When there's something on offer, some kind of gold or glory, recognition or reward, then there will be a way for some parties to...well, we can use the term "game", but one person's game is another person's strategic approach.

We all take our strategic approaches to the REF. We've had our conversations this week about what our REF strategy is going to be. Are we looking to achieve this or this, and is that a game? No, it's a strategy. We all do it.

If there's a lot of reward associated with something, there will be gamification or strategic behaviours.

Perverse incentives, there really can be. It's hard to always foresee what those incentives are going to be, but we do need to do that piece of thinking, hence the SCOPE framework. The P of SCOPE is this "probe" stage, to probe unintended consequences and gaming, discriminatory effects and so on.

Too often, we design assessments and we think "I've done it!" And we don't think, if this is used year on year on year, who's ultimately going to win and who's ultimately going to lose?

Assessments can be used to have intended consequences. That's what the REF Open Access policy was and did and achieved much higher levels of Open Access. But they're not always positive, and we need to at least do the piece of thinking, even if it's not always possible to get to the right conclusions on that.

Khan, Hamid 39:31

There's always a risk of perverse incentives, but if the thing that we are doing is providing the support for standard-setting and having policies around standard-setting, that could be one way that we can sort of marry the culture of recognition and incentives with the culture of Open Research.

The first phase of the project that we're doing on Beyond Open Research is looking at open research data, specifically. How can we improve transparency of research data? How can we improve the quality and the robustness of research data in a systemic way? Are there any specific challenges, and indeed opportunities and initiatives to be aware of when we're thinking about these questions are around research data?

Elizabeth Gadd 41:01

If you're looking at any form of recognition, incentivisation, assessment mechanism, I would definitely recommend the SCOPE framework to help with that piece of thinking. SCOPE is an acronym.

I've already mentioned the "probe" stage at the end. S is to "start" with what you actually value about the thing you're evaluating. [The University of] Surrey, for example, used the SCOPE framework to identify their own Open Research indicators, and by doing the "Start with what you value" bit recognised that it's not just about how many research datasets are in the repository this year [compared to] last year. It was some of the more qualitative stuff around understanding Open Research within the institution.

What is it that you care about when you have an ambition around high-quality research data? Is it just something more in the repository, or is it something else? Is it what having high-quality research data leads to ultimately? And if it's what research data leads to, what is it that it leads to? And, therefore, is it research data itself in and of itself that you want to be monitoring? Or is it something else? And if it's something else, how will you assess that? That is a really important first step.

A lot of Open Research indicator-type work starts and finishes with how much is in the repository. It's all numerical.

Have you come across the work of Ismael Rafols around Open Research assessment? They published something recently on the LSE Impact blog⁵ around this point. When we assess Open Research and data and everything else, we do tend to get fixated on the stuff rather than on the culture that we want to achieve through encouraging more people to do the stuff. It's not just counts of stuff that we should be investigating when we're looking at assessing Open Research, but attitudes towards it, institutional policies. That values piece is really important.

And then it's the "context" [C in SCOPE] piece that I was talking about earlier. What level are you talking about when assessing Open Research? Are you talking about assessing individuals? You're talking about research groups? You're talking about doing an institution-level assessment?

Then, why you're doing that kind of assessing or incentivising? Are you doing it because you want to show off about it? And are you doing it because you want to just monitor progress year on year? Are you're doing it because you want to be better than King's College, so is it about benchmarking? Is it because you want to reward people for doing the right things?

That context piece needs to be considered. And then you get to your options for evaluation – and this is where a lot of Open Research indicator stuff starts – it's like, "What else can we do with our bibliometric data?"

Dimensions⁶ have done it; they've got research integrity markers. PLOS [Public Library of Science]⁷ have done it. They've got all this stuff around Open Research indicators now, and it's all based on the bibliographic record.

Do we want to measure only the data that's associated with a journal article? No, we really don't want that because that just sends us back to the problem we've got in the first place, where everything is all focused on the journal article. The journal article becomes the accounting unit of scholarship. No, we've got to move beyond that.

⁵ See [The benefits of Open science are not inevitable: monitoring its development should be value-led | Impact of Social Sciences \(lse.ac.uk\)](#) [accessed: 4-9-2024].

⁶ See [Dimensions AI | The most advanced scientific research database](#) [accessed: 4-9-2024].

⁷ See [Home - PLOS](#) [accessed: 4-9-2024].

It's thinking about what options we have for assessing data, and this takes us down to the idea that the only tool available for assessing institutions' engagement with research data at the moment is Elsevier's Data Monitor. Because you've got so many repositories. Some is on the Arts and Humanities Data Service or some is on OSF [Open Science Framework] , some is elsewhere... you know? So, institutions don't really know how much data they've got because it's all over the place.

Elsevier come in and say, "We'll help you. Give us your money. We'll help you." Do we want to start measuring Open Research through closed mechanisms? No, we don't. Do we want to be measuring Open Research with commercial services? No, we don't. So then you've got the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information⁸. How can we, as institutions, make sure that we've got access to open data about open data, right? So that's our "options" [O in SCOPE] conversation. Then "probe" we've talked about already, and then E is to "evaluate", and evaluate your evaluation.

It's like the EIONs that we're doing here, Evidence-Informed Output Narratives. We're going to do it, but then there's going to be a really important evaluation stage because they might not work. The unintended consequences are not always foreseeable, and we want to just make sure that we got that right.

So, I would definitely point you towards SCOPE, and I can certainly point you towards other institutions who've used SCOPE to help their thinking on that.

Khan, Hamid 47:03

We're very keen not to reinvent the wheel, but to learn from other people, and hopefully through this project, others will learn from the work we've done as well.

It was interesting you mentioned Dimensions and their research integrity markers and the PLOS Open Science indicators. It's amplifying the same problem that we already have, partly in the sense you said that it's making everything about the journal article, and it's concentrating power in the hands of the publishers, but also it didn't strike me that there was any way to do anything about negative data as part of those initiatives, because if there's no journal article, there's no negative data. That's

⁸ See <https://barcelona-declaration.org/> [accessed: 4-9-2024].

yet another challenge that is not being addressed by the current publisher-focused models of Open Science indicators.

A slight change of topic: where do you think Team science fits into this, or does it fit into this? How can we strike the balance between the individual genius and the excellence of teams together?

Elizabeth Gadd 48:34

Coming back to the "context" stage of SCOPE, we need to think carefully about what level of granularity is legitimate to assess certain practices and certainly in terms of data.

All researchers produce data of some description, whether it's just a list of bibliographic references, or whether it's photographs or video, or hard numbers in spreadsheets. But, increasingly, even in arts and humanities disciplines, research is done in teams, and therefore is it appropriate to assess at the level of the individual?

It is a legitimate question, and I think largely you probably do want to assess at the level of the team, because that's how the research is done. But then, we don't recruit teams on the whole. There can be group hires, but we tend to focus very much on recruiting individuals, and therefore we need individual narratives and a sense of what individuals contribute.

The challenge with individual-level responsibility for Open Research is that if research has been done in a team, the ECR [early career researcher] may fight for all their worth to get their data made available openly, but if the PI [principal investigator] says no, then all the work of the ECR is just not recognised or rewarded in any way.

So, there is a clear argument for assessing a team level. With narrative CVs now, they're looking at team-level narrative CVs, but it does introduce a whole new layer of complexity around assessment and other operations as well.

Khan, Hamid 51:05

If there was just one thing that universities could do in the short to medium term that would help to shift the culture of recognition and incentives towards quality, what would you say that one thing is?

Elizabeth Gadd 51:25

You're not making this easy, are you?

Khan, Hamid 51:27

No, no. This might put you on the spot, I realise.

Elizabeth Gadd 51:33

The first thing that comes to mind is that qualitative things should be assessed in a qualitative way. If institutions did move away from more quantitative forms of assessment to more qualitative forms of assessment, the hope is that that would lead to formative forms of qualitative assessment.

We're not just saying, "That paper was really good and these are the reasons why". It would be formative forms of assessment, buddying, mentoring, where you send a draft, a half-complete draft of either a grant proposal or a paper to a colleague and get them to qualitatively assess it in a formative way.

Then the hope is that better quality outputs will result. We all moan about peer review, and sometimes it truly is of shocking quality, but on the whole most of us who've been through a peer review process, apart from the initial bruising that it gives you when you read the comments, will agree that the outcomes are generally better, the resulting paper is generally better than it would have been because you just got another pair of eyes on it.

That formative form of peer review is what I would immediately leap to if put on the spot like I just have been!

Khan, Hamid 53:34

Final question, then. Was there anything you were expecting to be asked that didn't come up today or that you would like to mention?

Elizabeth Gadd 53:45

I don't think so. We've talked about how assessing Open Research might not necessarily help us to deliver on Open Research, how we need to think a bit more carefully about our incentives and how what we disincentivise is just as important as what we incentivise, Open Research information, I think, is going to be the next big thing and how we work collectively, together, to ensure that our scholarly record is actually a scholarly record.